

16/2/19

Abstracts

13th International Conference

on

Development of Drylands

Converting Dryland Areas from
Grey into Green

February 11-14, 2019

Organised by

International Dryland Development Commission

and

Arid Zone Research Association of India

ICAR-Central Arid Zone Research Institute, Jodhpur, INDIA

T-6/P-2

Sehjan (*Moringa oleifera*) – Germplasm utilization and technological advancements for cultivation under dry-lands of Rajasthan

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Sehjan (*Moringa oleifera* Lam.) popularly known as moringa or drum-stick and native to India is versatile crop-plant due to its diverse uses (tender pods, leaves and flowers) and eco-restoration. Even-after lot of development in southern parts of the country, *sehjan* is still under-scored for dry-lands of Rajasthan. Realizing its numerous uses, ease of multiplication and cultivation, germplasm collection was started in 1995 at CIAH, Bikaner. Seedling population of annual moringa and limb-cuttings of elite-types were collected and evaluated. The seedling population of PKM-1 recorded wide variations for pod quality and bearing pattern under arid environment. The results of progeny testing from elite-types and four generation selection, the line AHMO-1-4s is developed and studied under varying situations from 2010 to 2016. It is fast growing, high yielding, drought tolerant genotype bearing medium sized pods of excellent quality. For developing nursery and field establishment techniques, experimental trails were conducted during 2015 to 2018. Freshly harvested seeds of May-June matured pods from mother plants of AHMO-1-4s were used for sowing (first week of June, July and August). Medium sized poly-tubes filled with 1:1:1 mixture of sheep-manure, vermi-compost and sandy-soil were sown with single seedbeg⁻¹. Nursery seedlings were 31.8-61.4 (av. 48.68) cm in height at 30-60 d, and recorded 54.6-78.6 (av. 68.62) per cent field survival. With *khejri* based production sites, KM-9 model (24×4×4 m) and moringa planting system (4×4 m) is best for optimal resource utilization, organic culture and higher bio-mass production. Since, it is damaged by low temperature and frost conditions, it is recommended that moringa plants should be pruned or headed-back at 30-45 cm height from ground-level in the last week of December month to save the established plantations under hot arid agro-climate.

